

What's in a name? That which we call a receptor

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In science, there are instances where scientific terms are not crucial, but other times, they are essential. Using the appropriate scientific terms may unite diverse researchers and allow us to create and test hypotheses that we haven't considered before. My efforts to request researchers to consider some of the metal-binding proteins and gas-sensing proteins as metalloreceptors or gasoreceptors received a mixed response from the scientific community to which I presented it. My intention is not to introduce new terms for receptors, but rather to stress that as we trace back evolutionary times, the number of receptors per ligand can be several orders of magnitude greater than what we have traditionally accepted to date. In this manuscript, building upon the adage from William Shakespeare's play *Romeo and Juliet*, I present my arguments on the importance of scientific terms when it comes to receptors for metal ions and gaseous signaling molecules. Accepting the complexity of protein-based metalloreceptors and gasoreceptors may help us tackle societal challenges that include civilizational diseases and gasocrine-/photocrine-based inter-organismal communication.

What's in a name? That which we call a receptor,

By any other name would sense as strong.

What's in a name? That which we call an affair or a scandal,

By any other name would stir as much intrigue.

What's in a name? That which we call an animal or a lion,

By any other name would still command respect.

What's in a name? That which we call a carbon or a diamond,

By any other name would still hold slaves.

What's in a name? That which we call a crown of wood or a crown of thorns,

By any other name would still denote suffering.

What's in a name? That which we call a diplomat or a spy,

By any other name would still wield artful lie.

What's in a name? That which we call a doctor or a dentist,

By any other name would still mend with gentle hands.

What's in a name? That which we call an elephant or a Ganesh,

By any other name would still hold wisdom's sacred mesh.

What's in a name? That which we call an explosive or a nuclear weapon,

By any other name would still bring devastation's burden.

What's in a name? That which we call a flirt or a harasser,

By any other name would still dictate boundaries to consider.

What's in a name? That which we call a fortress or a prison,

By any other name would still confine the soul within.

What's in a name? That which we call a foul-smelling chamber or a gas chamber,

By any other name would still evoke horror and disaster.

What's in a name? That which we call a hero or a foe,
By any other name would still shape the stories we know.
What's in a name? That which we call a hero or a heretic,
By any other name would still ignite beliefs eclectic.
What's in a name? That which we call a leader or a dictator,
By any other name would still wield dark power.
What's in a name? That which we call a light or big bang,
By any other name would question the creator.
What's in a name? That which we call a murzyn or Mandela,
By any other name would still carry histories of valor.
What's in a name? That which we call a nigger or a King,
By any other name would still carry dignity's ring.
What's in a name? That which we call a promise or a pretext,
By any other name would still shape trust or regret.
What's in a name? That which we call a river or the Ganges,
By any other name would still souls flow.
What's in a name? That which we call a service center or a brothel,
By any other name would still hold secrets to dispel.
What's in a name? That which we call a teacher or a mentor,
By any other name would still guide with wisdom's fervor.
What's in a name? That which we call a wife or a partner,
By any other name would still hold anchor.
What's in a name? That which we call a writer or a poet,
By any other name would still make hearts float.

What's in a name? That which we call a sensor or a receptor,

By any other name would still denote the creator's intention.

What's in a name? That which we call a transcription factor or a receptor.

By any other name would still explain the creator's action.

What's in a name? That which we call a metal-binding protein or a metalloreceptor.

By any other name would still explain the creator's message.

What's in a name? That which we call a receptor,

By any other name would sense as strong.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

DISCLOSURE

The author used ChatGPT for predicting some of the verses. The author takes full responsibility for the content of this manuscript. The funding agency and institution S.A. is affiliated with was not involved in the contents of the manuscript.